

DAIRY 4.0 AND ITS DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS

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The application of innovative technological solutions and the automation of various processes in the national economy are of crucial importance in addressing the shortage of natural resources and emerging global challenges associated with the world's growing population. In light of this, the emergence of the concept of the fourth industrial revolution (Industry 4.0) aims to support efficient and sustainable production by integrating advanced digital technologies, tools, and resources. The rapid development of Industry 4.0 represents a true solution to these pressing issues.

Industry 4.0 enables real-time internet connectivity for various layers of data sources and allows for fast and efficient processing of large volumes of data. This ensures rapid production of high-quality products that meet demand in manufacturing and facilitates integration between different systems. Industry 4.0, which incorporates numerous advanced sensor technologies, can improve the technological structure of the dairy sector, an important link in the food industry.

In line with the development of industrial generations, new principles such as PLF (Precision Livestock Farming), PDF (Precision Dairy Farming), SFM (Smart Farming Management), and Dairy 4.0 with modern technological support are emerging in the livestock sector over the next decade. These principles offer significant opportunities, including automatic manure cleaning in farm buildings, microclimate control, remote identification and inventory of cattle through electronic chips, collection of information about objects via non-invasive and invasive sensors and IoT devices, robotic control, optimal feeding tailored to individual animals, monitoring milk parameters during the milking process, early detection of cattle diseases, application of artificial intelligence tools based on big data, effective breeding and decision-making, and most importantly, reducing human intervention and managing resource efficiency through online management. In particular, the adoption of these innovative technologies in line with Industry 4.0 has led to the establishment of new dairy farms known as "Dairy 4.0."

The developmental stages of the dairy industry are distinguished from one another by several characteristics, including the technologies employed, methods of implementing feed and breeding practices, data analysis techniques,

and the farm's environmental impact. Below, we will explore the distinctive features of the periods from Dairy 1.0 to Dairy 4.0, as well as the key components of Dairy 4.0.

Figure 1.

Dairy 1.0 (Traditional) dairy farming employs a conventional approach with minimal automation, relying primarily on manual labor. Animal feeding, milking, health monitoring, and breeding processes are conducted based on human observation and intervention. Furthermore, there is minimal attention to environmental impact, limited veterinary services, and the collection and management of records are predominantly carried out manually using paper-based systems.

Dairy 2.0 (Mechanized) represents the modernization era of the dairy industry. It primarily involves implementing key mechanization methods to reduce human labor on farms. Practices such as ration-based feeding of farm animals, controlled breeding, and improved healthcare protocols have been introduced. While records are still maintained on paper, the requirements for data management and collection have evolved, incorporating the results of scientific research.

Dairy 3.0 (Automated) is characterized by this period of dairy farming and the introduction of milking machines and specialized mechanisms. This phase involves implementing improved feeding practices, artificial insemination and effective breeding management, ensuring optimal microclimate conditions, reducing the farm's environmental impact, disease detection and management, as well as, most crucially, maintaining electronic records and conducting data analysis.

Dairy 4.0 (Smart Farm) represents the most advanced stage of the dairy industry, integrating modern technologies to optimize all processes, manage the farm territory technologically, ensure sustainability, and minimize negative

environmental impacts. The essential components that constitute the 4th generation of the dairy industry are shown in Figure 2, and their important aspects will now be examined.

2-rasm. Dairy 4.0 ni tashkil qiluvchi komponentlar

Robotics is one of the latest developing technologies in the dairy industry, which includes robotic automatic milking systems, waste removal systems, and individual cattle feeding systems. In particular, automatic milking systems allow for a significant increase in milking frequency and productivity by reducing labor costs, while manure removal systems help prevent risks to cow health and reduce ammonia gas emissions. Sensors installed in robotic systems enable the collection of accurate real-time data, which can be used to analyze daily milk yield and parameters, as well as predict important values (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The role of robotic systems in the dairy industry

3D printing is a production system that allows for controlling the shape and structural ingredients of food products, as well as meeting individual nutritional requirements. Currently, this is being used in the production of meat and meat analogues, egg whites, and protein products. The scope of 3D printing in dairy products is primarily characterized by the following five key concepts: innovative, futuristic, healthy, efficient, and sustainable.

Big Data methods bring significant benefits to dairy farms (Figure 4), including improving dairy farm management, predicting milk productivity, enhancing quality and quantity, and facilitating both operational and strategic decision-making. BigData helps identify and predict milk productivity and diseases at both individual cow and herd levels, assists in herd formation, and contributes to improving farm profitability. BigData is formed as a result of collecting and integrating various property data of real-time objects into a central database. Currently, important studies in farm practices are achieving successful results, such as forming nutritional groups, assessing animal health, predicting early clinical mastitis and lameness, and obtaining maximum profit with minimal costs.

Figure 4. Benefits of Big Data for the dairy industry

IoT (Internet of Things) is a standalone operational tool that enables the collection of various real-time data about objects, performs initial processing, and transmits this information to computing nodes in a communication environment. For instance, IoT devices that monitor cows' temperature, heart rate, and movement patterns provide information about their health, location, and activity levels. IoT applications vary depending on the issue being addressed, but their operating mechanisms are almost identical. They typically consist of a complex including sensors, connection to a communication network, memory, control and processing board, power source, motor drive, and information input and output components. Data obtained from the sensors are recorded in memory, initially processed, compared with standards, and, if necessary, messages are transmitted to other nodes. In animal husbandry, IoT tools are used for animal monitoring, health control, and automation of farming operations.

Artificial intelligence (AI) is primarily used to assess the health and well-being of dairy animals for milk productivity. In this case, AI simplifies the decision-making processes by utilizing a range of data sources about an individual, from highly important to seemingly unnecessary information gathered from rarely used source. AI determines the requirements for effective cow management based on physiological and environmental factors, which helps ensure high-quality milk production. Dairy 4.0 utilizes AI to improve product quality, meet customer demands, and enhance dairy farm practices.

Blockchain is a new technology that is rapidly penetrating various fields. This technology enables customers to track the production and quality of their products. Blockchain technology is being applied in the development of smart ecosystems for milk supply chains to help provide sustainable and safe food for the growing global population. In her research study, Mangla investigated how

blockchain technology can be utilized to enhance the social sustainability of milk supply chains in Turkey. They have identified several advantages of this technology, including preventing food fraud, developing rural areas, protecting animal welfare and health, and ensuring food security.

In conclusion, the Dairy 4.0 concept represents a crucial step towards digitalization and automation in the dairy industry. Its implementation not only enhances production efficiency but also strengthens food security, protects the environment, and enables more effective utilization of human resources. In the future, as a result of integrating technologies such as artificial intelligence and blockchain in this direction, "smart farms" are expected to develop further, leading to the emergence of sustainable and cost-effective systems that meet the demands of the global dairy market.

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